

Remotisation technologies for enabling access; *from software and robots to protocols and policies*

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Information Technology and the continuous advances of computing have dramatically altered not only the way we store and process information but also the way we socially interact and communicate. Most notably systems like the simple email, chatting software, video calls, collaboration boards, and social networking platforms are widely used daily both for personal and professional purposes. The challenges introduced by the COVID-19 crisis required a prompt and effective response that was mostly based on existing technologies but also promoted the development of new ones.

Elettra took multiple strategic actions in order to continue its service towards the scientific community. Such actions included the continuous operation of the ELETTRA synchrotron and FERMI FEL accelerators coupled with preferential and fast track proposal management with mail-in services. In addition to that, it funded an internal project for introducing remotisation technologies to its beamlines thus assisting their operation during the crisis.

The project named Essential Remotisation (EsRe) aims at fostering remote experimental station control, scientific data acquisition and archiving according to FAIR principles, promoting a more Open science. In addition to that, with an interdisciplinary team including beamline scientists and computing engineers, EsRe will critically examine robotic systems for telepresence and sample transport, augmented reality glasses, and collaborative systems for distributed lab-books and experiment logging (Fig. 1).

The promotion of remotisation goes beyond the COVID-19 crisis since its technologies assist automatization and can be of help to the Elettra personnel and the visiting researchers. Elettra over the past 10 years has been involved in relevant EU projects like PaNdata-ODI, CALIPSOplus, and nowadays Ex-PaNDS and PaNOSC (with CERIC-ERIC). Such projects inspired common data formats, scientific data policies, data cataloging, FAIR principles, computing in EOSC, and the use of DOIs.

Beyond the remotisation technology and its supporting policies, the new mode of operation requires wider cultural changes with expected impact on the way science is done. It should be easier to form geographically dispersed research teams that remotely collaborate and efficiently use instrumentation all over the world.

Elettra through the use of remotisation technologies will continue to provide its services aiming at offering improved ways of performing experiments in its

beamlines and labs. Suitable strategic planning and funds allocation will make the most out of existing technologies while exploring future IT developments.

Figure 1: Simplified illustration of on-site beamline personnel collaborating with his off-site team through means of remote desktop software, data sharing and telepresence robots.

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